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Assessing the Impact of Socially Unacceptable Extreme Discourses on the General Population

Work package 2 – Deliverable 2.1

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1. Executive Summary

This report presents findings on the effects of socially unacceptable extreme discourses (SUEDs) in the context of migration, contributing to the DEMINE project's broader objective of understanding communication dynamics related to migration, polarisation, and social cohesion in Europe. The report focuses on SUEDs, including hate speech, threat-based narratives and populist messaging, and investigates how these shape public perceptions, emotional responses and political behavior. While harmful migration-related discourse has been widely documented, less is known about how it is interpreted by individuals and through which mechanisms it influences attitudes and behaviour. Moving beyond a sole focus on exposure, the report highlights the role of perceived threat, emotional responses, and individual predispositions in shaping reactions to such content.

To do so, the deliverable combines complementary methodological approaches. First, it draws on a cross-national panel survey conducted among representative samples in Belgium (N= 2017) and Italy (N= 2991), capturing self-reported exposure to immigration-related hateful content alongside desensitisation to hateful content towards migrants, stereotypes, and behavioral intentions. Second, it includes three survey experiments conducted in Flanders, identifying the causal effects of message characteristics such as framing, political positioning, and source attribution on emotional responses, threat perceptions, acceptability, and political evaluations. Together, these approaches provide both descriptive and causal evidence on how migration-related discourse is perceived and evaluated.

The findings show that the effects of SUEDs operate through emotional and perceptual mechanisms. **Survey data** indicate that exposure to hateful migration-related content is not directly associated with reduced emotional responsiveness. Instead, higher desensitisation to hateful content towards migrants is linked to more negative perceptions and greater support for both activism and more extreme forms of political action. This suggests that individuals who are less emotionally influenced by hate (more desensitised), also have more negative views on migrants and are more willing to take political action. Importantly, more frequent contact with immigrants is associated with more positive perceptions and less desensitisation to hate, while showing no relationship with support for extreme political action. Migration background, by contrast, plays only a limited role. These findings suggest that individual experiences and perceptions are more strongly linked to outcomes than socio-demographic background alone. **Experimental evidence** focuses on mechanisms underlying these patterns. Exposure to threat-based content increases negative emotional responses, which in turn heightens perceptions of immigration-related threats and leads to more negative attitudes. Across these analyses, perceived threat emerges as a central factor shaping political preferences: higher perceived threat is associated with increased support for restrictive, right-leaning policy solutions, decreased support for humanitarian approaches, and greater perceived effectiveness of restrictive political solutions. In contrast, the role of message source is limited, suggesting that audience characteristics matter more than who delivers the message. Overall, the societal impact of harmful migration-related discourse depends less on exposure alone and more on how such content is interpreted.

The report contributes to the DEMINE research agenda by providing an integrated empirical assessment of harmful migration-related discourse across contexts and methods. It highlights the value of combining real-world exposure data with experimental evidence and calls for moving toward a more nuanced understanding of how message characteristics interact with audience responses. The report concludes that mitigating the impact of SUEDs requires going beyond reducing exposure and addressing the emotional and cognitive processes through which such content influences public opinion. It recommends that future research and policy focus on perceptions, emotional

responsiveness, and audience heterogeneity, and develop strategies that engage with how individuals interpret migration-related information.

2. About DEMINE

DEMINE goals

Globalisation and immigration have altered intercommunity relations, leading to a rise in intergroup conflict marked by discrimination against diverse minorities. This has given way to various forms of radicalisation and extremism, spanning religious, political, and xenophobic spectrums worldwide. Globalisation and immigration strain social cohesion (shared public values, group norms, guiding principles) in numerous countries. While individual attitudes may not have shifted significantly, the prominence of migration in public discourse and the polarisation of public opinion have increased substantially. As a result, a divided public opinion has become more overtly hostile towards migration.

The DEMINE (DEaling with conflicts related to MIgration: NEgotiating social cohesion through communication) European Joint Doctorate (DN-JD) network is a collaborative effort across disciplines. Its primary goal is to enhance Europe's capacity to address a significant challenge: the rise of various forms of radicalisation and extremism that pose a threat to social cohesion. Through a combination of inter-sectoral mobility and a balanced blend of research and transferable competences, DEMINE develops a much-needed framework on the role and interplay of interpersonal and mediated communication in intergroup relations and conflict related to migration and globalisation, ultimately contributing to social cohesion. DEMINE has crafted a comprehensive research and training programme to examine the complex relationships between various forms of communication, including traditional media, social media, and interpersonal interactions. This programme aims to understand how various communication channels shape individual attitudes and beliefs regarding migration, as well as their impact on intergroup dynamics (social cohesion), especially within the broader context of political and societal polarisation, and the processes of radicalisation, with a specific focus on migration-related aspects.

DEMINE Educational Goals

- Train nine doctoral candidates to become the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers skilled in digital methods, participatory community research, and the evaluation of intergroup conflicts.
- Equip candidates with advanced theoretical and practical knowledge, focusing on strategic analysis, community-based participatory youth work, and open-source intelligence techniques.
- Develop transferable skills such as self-management, inter-sectoral collaboration, and innovation-oriented thinking to prepare candidates for both academic and non-academic careers.
- Promote interdisciplinary and international mobility, enabling candidates to apply their research findings in real-world contexts and contribute to professional fields ranging from strategic analysis to media production.

DEMINE Research Goals

- Identify and analyse the differences and similarities across various forms of socially unacceptable, extreme discourse, particularly related to migration, at the intersections of politics, media, and interpersonal communication.
- Investigate the impact of extreme discourse on individual attitudes and beliefs, with a specific focus on adolescents and vulnerable populations, while understanding the socio-demographic and psychological factors influencing susceptibility.

- Develop countermeasures to empower adolescents, news media producers, and political actors to mitigate the societal impact of divisive discourse, fostering social cohesion and reinforcing democratic principles.
- Provide a nuanced, cross-cultural, and interdisciplinary understanding of the mechanisms of polarisation and radicalisation to inform effective strategies and policy interventions.

By integrating these educational and research goals, DEMINE aims to enhance Europe's capacity to address the growing societal challenges linked to migration, fostering resilience and inclusivity in an increasingly polarised world.

DEMINE Consortium

DEMINE consists of three academic partners namely, KU Leuven, Aarhus Universitet, and Università Degli Studi di Padova as well as nine non-academic partners including OCAM-OCAD, City of Mechelen, Textgain, The Migration Policy Group, Refugees Welcome, Institut for Menneskerettigheder, Stichting Bellingcat, Verwey-Jonker Institute, and Hannah Arendt Institute.

The DEMINE consortium will train nine doctoral candidates (DCs) within a cross-disciplinary and international environment, giving them the opportunity to network, study and collect data in Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe (see secondments) in collaboration with academic and non-academic experts, with ample opportunities to develop transferable skills such as technology literacy, adaptability (i.e., not feeling helpless in the face of change), strong communication skills, and ability to work in a team, in a dependable and well-organised fashion.

3. Introduction

Immigration has become one of the most polarised political issues in Europe, increasingly characterised by affective polarisation, hostility toward outgroups, and uncivil discourse (Gethin et al., 2022; Simonsen & Bonikowski, 2022; Gidron et al., 2023; Renström et al., 2023). Central to this development is the way migration is communicated in public debate. Immigration has been found to be framed as a threat (cultural, economic, or safety) in both, the traditional and social media which has been shown to shape public attitudes, emotions, and policy preferences (Brouwer et al., 2017; Vétois et al., 2025; Matthes et al., 2024). These dynamics are further amplified by socially unacceptable extreme discourses (SUEDs), including hate speech, disinformation, and populist rhetoric, which circulate widely in digital environments and can intensify perceptions of threat and intergroup hostility (Pöyhtäri et al., 2021; Soral et al., 2018; Vasilopoulos et al., 2019).

A growing body of research suggests that exposure to such discourses influences individuals through several mechanisms. In this report, we focus on three in particular: affective, normalizing, and polarisation processes. At the affective level, populist communication and threat-based framing have been shown to elicit emotional response, especially anger, which play a role in shaping political outcomes, including affective polarisation (Renström et al., 2023), support for far-right actors (Vasilopoulos et al., 2019), and attitudes toward migration (Matthes et al., 2023). Repeated exposure to hate speech can lead to desensitisation, reducing emotional responsiveness, and making such content appear less harmful, which in turn increases prejudice toward targeted groups (Soral et al., 2018). At the normalizing level, the frequent presence of derogatory language can contribute to the normalisation of hate speech, as individuals come to perceive it as more common and therefore more socially acceptable, eroding existing anti-discrimination norms (Bilewicz & Soral, 2020). At a broader level, these processes may also reinforce polarisation, as exposure to hostile and exclusionary rhetoric, especially coming from political figures, strengthens ingroup-outgroup distinctions and increases support for more extreme positions and political behaviour (Piazza 2020). Countering these dynamics, scholars have long recognised that intergroup contact can reduce prejudice (Pettigrew & Tropp, 2006) and threat perceptions (Stephan and Stephan, 2015). There should also be a greater reduction in prejudice in optimal conditions such as equal status, common goals, cooperation, and support of authorities, law, or custom (Pettigrew & Tropp, 2006), though negative contact can also heighten threat perceptions (Plant and Devine, 2003; Stephan and Stephan, 2015).

Taken together, the effects of SUEDs are multifaceted, operating through emotional, cognitive, and social pathways. Rather than exposure alone being the primary driver, the way individuals interpret and respond to such content, particularly in terms of perceived threat and perceived acceptability, appears to be crucial. Building on this perspective, the present studies examine how exposure to migration-related SUEDs influences perceived harmfulness, emotional reactions, stereotypes, and behavioural intentions, and whether these effects differ across national contexts. To do so, it combines panel survey data from Belgium and Italy with three survey experiments conducted in Flanders. This integrated approach captures both exposure to harmful migration-related content and the causal effects of specific message characteristics, providing a comprehensive account of how SUEDs shape perceptions, emotions, and political responses.

4. Methodology

This report consists of data from two different methodologies. The first part is based on a longitudinal panel survey within the Belgian and Italian general population. The second part is based on three experimental studies in Belgium. Together, these data provide both correlational (panel) and causal

(experiments) evidence on how migration-related discourses are encountered, interpreted, and evaluated.

4.1 Two-country panel survey

The first part of this report draws on data from a panel survey conducted in Belgium and Italy. The panel survey examines exposure to migration-related hateful content, emotional reactivity to online hate, stereotypes, and support for activism and radicalism. Data collection took place simultaneously in both countries between January 9 and February 9, 2026. The panel survey provides descriptive insight into how frequently individuals are exposed to hateful migration-related content in everyday life and how such exposure relates to key attitudinal and behavioural outcomes.

4.1.1. Sample

Data were collected with the help of Bilendi online panel among adults aged 18 and older. The sample comprised 2,017 respondents in Belgium and 2,991 in Italy.

In the Belgian sample, 42.7% identified as male and 57.0% as female, with a mean age of 49.2 years ($SD = 15.6$). Educational attainment was distributed across low (10.2%), medium (37.0%), and high (52.8%) levels. In the Italian sample, 45.8% identified as male and 54.1% as female, with a mean age of 43.4 years ($SD = 14.1$). Education was predominantly medium (51.4%), followed by high (42.5%) and low (6.1%). Both samples over-represent women and higher education levels relative to national population benchmarks, which is typical of online panel research and should be considered when interpreting the findings. Ten respondents with implausible or missing age values were excluded from analyses.

4.1.2. Procedure

The survey was administered online. At first participants were asked to give their informed consent in order to take part in the study. The survey took approximately 10–15 minutes to complete.

The study was approved by the Social and Societal Ethics Committee (SMEC) of KU Leuven [G-2025-10356].

4.1.3 Measures

Participants reported how often they *encountered hateful or hostile content about migrants on social media*. Beyond exposure, we measured several potential outcomes: emotional *desensitisation to hateful migration content*, intentions to *engage in both conventional activism and more extreme radical action* on immigration issues, and *stereotypes* toward immigrants across two dimensions: perceived *competence and warmth*. We also assessed *contact with immigrants* from both European and non-European backgrounds, and whether participants themselves had a *migration background*. Full details on all scales and item wording are provided in Appendix A.

4.2 Experimental studies

Three survey experiments were conducted in Flanders (Dutch-speaking Belgium). The experiments examined how different migration-related frames, sources, and messages influence threat perceptions, emotions, attitudes, political support, and hate acceptance. The experiments complement the survey by testing the causal effects of different message characteristics under controlled conditions.

4.2.1. Sample

All three experiments were conducted within the same survey among adult members of an online survey panel BPact in Flanders.

- **Experiment 1** (July 2025) included 748 participants who completed the survey (45.3% male, 53.9% female, 0.8% non-binary; $Mage = 46.8$, $SD = 17.4$; low education 11.7%, medium 39.2%, high 49.1%).
- **Experiments 2 and 3** (July 2025) share the same sample ($N = 1,013$) (48.0% male, 51.3% female, 0.7% non-binary; $Mage = 49.7$, $SD = 17.7$; low education 16.2%, medium 40.7%, high 43.1%).

Participants were adults (18+) from the Dutch-speaking part of Belgium. Across studies, sampling was based on representativeness in age, gender, and education. However, samples skewed somewhat older and more highly educated relative to the general Flemish population, a pattern typical of online panel research. Participants provided informed consent prior to participation.

4.2.2. Experiment 1

Design and procedure

Experiment 1 used a between-subjects design in which respondents were randomly assigned to view either an immigration-related post framed as threatening, framed neutrally, or unrelated control content within a simulated social media feed. After exposure, respondents reported negative emotions (anger, anxiety), immigration-related threat perceptions, and immigration attitudes. This experiment isolates the causal effect of threat-based media framing on emotional responses and attitudes toward immigration within a simulated social media feed.

Picture 1. Examples of the simulated social media feed and the threat framed news post.

Measures

Participants' emotional responses were captured through self-reported *anger* and *anxiety*. We further measured *perceptions of threat* related to immigration, covering symbolic, realistic, safety, and social cohesion concerns. Finally, we assessed *general attitudes toward immigration*, reflecting the degree of opposition to immigration. Full details on all scales and item wording are provided in Appendix A.

4.2.3. Experiment 2

Design and procedure

Experiment 2 randomly assigned participants to view either a left-wing, centrist, or right-wing political message about immigration presented in X (former Twitter) post format. The left-wing message framed migration as a humanitarian issue linked to global injustice and advocated open borders, equal rights, and solidarity. The right-wing message framed migration as a problem of border control and public protection, emphasizing restrictive measures such as faster returns and stopping irregular crossings. The centrist message framed migration as a matter of governance and system effectiveness, proposing a combination of firm borders and compassionate administration. After exposure, respondents evaluated the message's effectiveness and personal relevance and indicated their willingness to support a political party endorsing the proposal. This experiment examines how perceived threat translates into political evaluations and support for political solutions.

Picture 2. Examples of the political messages framed as left-wing, centrist, and right-wing.

Measures

We measured *perceptions of threat* related to immigration across six dimensions: symbolic, realistic, safety, social cohesion, prejudice, and altruistic threat. We also assessed three responses to proposed immigration-related policy solution: how likely participants would be to *politically support* the proposal, how *effective* they perceived it to be, and how *personally relevant* they found the message. Full details on all scales and item wording are provided in Appendix A.

4.2.4 Experiment 3

Experiment 3 used a within-subjects design in which participants evaluated the same hateful migration-related message when attributed to different source types: a politician, journalist, celebrity, or unknown social media user. After each message, respondents rated its harmfulness and acceptability. This experiment tests whether the perceived source of hateful messages influences how such content is evaluated in terms of harmfulness and acceptability, and how individuals' predispositions, threat perception and political orientation influence this.

Picture 3. Example of the hateful messages from two different sources; journalist and unknown.

Measures

After viewing each social media post, participants rated how *harmful* and how *acceptable* they found the message. We additionally measured broader *perceptions of threat* related to immigration, capturing symbolic, realistic, safety, social cohesion, altruistic, and prejudice-related concerns. Full details on all scales and item wording are provided in Appendix A.

5. Results

The results are presented in three parts. First, we examine exposure to hateful immigration-related content and desensitisation to online hate in the Belgian and Italian panel survey. Second, we assess how framing immigration as a threat and via political lenses affect emotions and support for immigration policy solutions in two survey experiments. Third, we examine whether hateful immigration messages are evaluated differently depending on who is perceived to have expressed them.

5.1 How common is exposure and what is it associated with? (Panel Findings)

Country differences

Country comparisons revealed consistent differences between Belgian and Italian respondents (see Figure 1). Italian participants reported significantly higher exposure to hateful immigration-related content ($M = 3.22$) than Belgian respondents ($M = 2.72$), $t(4534.3) = -10.26$, $p < .001$. In contrast, Belgian respondents exhibited slightly higher levels of desensitisation ($M = 3.38$) compared to Italian respondents ($M = 3.21$), $t(4164.1) = 4.52$, $p < .001$. No significant country differences were observed for stereotypes (competence, $t(4314.2) = 0.53$, $p = .594$; warmth, $t(4350.9) = 1.07$, $p = .287$).

Support for both activism and radicalism were substantially higher in Italy than in Belgium. For activism intentions, respondents in Italy ($M = 3.50$) reported higher levels than those in Belgium ($M = 2.83$), $t(4400.1) = -17.90$, $p < .001$. A similar pattern was observed for radicalism intentions, with higher scores in Italy ($M = 2.54$) than in Belgium ($M = 1.92$), $t(4768.6) = -16.44$, $p < .001$.

In addition, Belgian respondents reported significantly more frequent contact with immigrants than Italian respondents, both for individuals with a European immigrant background ($M = 3.07$ vs. 2.67), $t(4181.8) = 11.69$, $p < .001$, and those with a non-European immigrant background ($M = 2.82$ vs. 2.59), $t(4189.7) = 6.79$, $p < .001$.

Country differences in exposure and key outcomes

Points show means and error bars show 95% confidence intervals

Figure 1. Country differences in key variables. Points show means and error bars represent 95% confidence intervals. Note. Contact with immigrants combines European and non-European immigrant contact.

Exposure to hateful content and Desensitisation

Contrary to expectations, self-reported exposure to hateful content was not meaningfully associated with desensitisation. The correlation between exposure and desensitisation was essentially zero in Belgium ($r = -.001, p = .96$) and very small in Italy ($r = .04, p = .015$) (see Figure 2). These results suggest that higher self-reported exposure does not necessarily correspond to greater emotional desensitisation to hateful content.

Desensitisation, Stereotypes, and Radicalism

Desensitisation showed strong and consistent associations with key outcome variables (see Figure 2). In both countries, lower emotional responsiveness (higher desensitisation) was associated with lower support for both activism (Belgium: $r = -.15, p < .001$; Italy: $r = -.14, p < .001$) and higher support for radicalism intentions (Belgium: $r = .21, p < .001$; Italy: $r = .29, p < .001$). This pattern is consistent with the idea that emotional responsiveness to hateful content may be linked to the form that political engagement takes, though the directionality of these associations cannot be established from correlational data alone.

At the same time, desensitisation was negatively associated with stereotype warmth and competence, suggesting that reduced emotional responsiveness is linked to less favourable evaluations of outgroups. In contrast, contact with immigrants showed a different pattern. More frequent contact was modestly associated with more positive stereotypes (warmth and competence; $r \approx .15-.20, p < .001$), more frequent exposure to hate (Belgium: $r = .17, p < .001$; Italy: $r = .20, p < .001$), and less desensitisation (Belgium: $r = -.17, p < .001$; Italy: $r = -.12, p < .001$). However, contact showed little to no association with radicalism intentions and only weak associations with activism. Immigration background, by contrast, was only weakly related to these variables and showed no meaningful

association with radicalism intentions, suggesting that individual experiences and perceptions are more strongly linked to these outcomes than socio-demographic background.

Taken together, these findings suggest that emotional responsiveness to hateful content (desensitisation) and interpersonal contact capture distinct but complementary dynamics: while desensitisation is more closely linked to more negative perceptions and support for extreme political action, contact with immigrants is more consistently associated with more positive perceptions, more frequent self-reported exposure, and stronger emotional reactions to hateful content (less desensitisation), indicating that potentially those more in contact with immigrants may be more likely to recognise online hate and be negatively emotionally affected by it.

Figure 2. Correlation matrices for Belgium and Italy showing relationships between exposure to hateful content, desensitisation, stereotypes, activism and radicalism intentions, RWA, and contact with immigrants. Colours indicate the strength and direction of correlations.

5.2 How do frames shape reactions and policy support? (Experiments 1 & 2)

The two framing experiments examine different responses to immigration-related discourse: Experiment 1 focuses on emotional reactions to threat-based media framing, while Experiment 2 examines how perceived threat shapes evaluations of political messages and support for political solutions.

Emotional Effects of Threat-Based Framing (Experiment 1)

Experiment 1 examined how exposure to threat-based versus neutral immigration content influences emotional responses and attitudes (see Figure 3).

Results show that threat-framed content significantly increased negative emotional reactions compared to the neutral and control content, particularly anxiety, $F(2, 729) = 44.33, p < .001, \eta^2p = .11$, and anger, $F(2, 729) = 31.35, p < .001, \eta^2p = .08$. In contrast, no significant effects were observed on immigration-related threat perceptions, $F(2, 729) = 1.35, p = .36$, or immigration attitudes, $F(2, 729) = 0.18, p = .83$. This indicates that exposure to threatening content primarily affected emotional responses rather than directly shifting attitudes. However, the absolute levels of reported emotions were relatively low across all conditions, indicating that while the effects are statistically robust, the overall intensity of emotional responses remains modest. This pattern is not unexpected, given that participants were passively scrolling through a feed without being instructed to attend closely to the content, and that the stimuli was relatively mild.

Although no direct attitudinal effects were found, additional analyses found emotional responses (both anxiety and anger) positively associated with perceived threat (e.g., $bs \approx 0.09\text{--}0.12, ps < .05$), which in turn strongly predicted more negative immigration attitudes ($b = 0.60, p < .001$). This pattern indicates that framing effects may operate through a gradual emotional pathway rather than immediate opinion change.

Figure 3. Adjusted means (with 95% confidence intervals) for anger, anxiety, immigration attitudes, and threat perception across the control, neutral, and threat conditions

Political Framing and Support for Policy Solutions (Experiment 2)

Experiment 2 examined how differently framed political messages about immigration influence political solutions support and evaluations. In particular, the analysis focused on the role of perceived immigration-related threat as a key factor shaping political preferences.

Results show that perceived immigration-related threat strongly shaped political preferences, $R^2 = .46$, $F(13, 990) = 63.66$, $p < .001$. Higher perceived threat was associated with decreased support for left-wing solutions ($b = -0.92$, $p < .001$) and increased support for both centrist ($b = 0.50$, $p < .001$) and especially right-wing solutions ($b = 1.03$, $p < .001$).

Importantly, these effects differed significantly across political framings. The interaction between perceived threat and political framing was strong, particularly for the left-wing condition ($b = -1.42$, $p < .001$), and smaller but still significant for the right-wing condition ($b = 0.53$, $p < .001$). This indicates that the impact of threat depends on how solutions are framed politically. At low or moderate levels of perceived threat, centrist solutions received the highest overall support. However, as perceived threat increased, support for right-wing solutions rose more steeply and eventually surpassed centrist support.

Figure 4. Predicted support for left-wing, centrist, and right-wing policy solutions across levels of perceived immigration threat. As perceived threat increases, support for left-wing solutions declines, while support for right-wing solutions rises sharply and eventually surpasses support for centrist solutions. Shaded areas represent 95% confidence intervals.

Additional analyses indicate that perceived threat also shapes how policy proposals are evaluated. Higher threat levels were associated with increased perceived effectiveness and relevance of right-wing proposals (e.g., interaction $bs \approx 0.29-0.35$, $ps \leq .001$), while evaluations of left-wing proposals became more negative (e.g., $bs \approx -0.81$ to -1.03 , $ps < .001$).

Overall, these findings suggest that threat perceptions not only directly influence political support but also alter the evaluative lens through which policy solutions are judged, reinforcing support for more restrictive approaches.

Taken together, the two framing experiments suggest that immigration-related discourse shapes emotional reactions, while political preferences are strongly associated with individuals' pre-existing perceptions of threat.

5.3 Source Effects and Audience Predispositions (Experiment 3)

Finally, a third experiment examines whether the perceived source of a hostile immigration-related message affects how harmful or acceptable it is judged to be.

Across sources, hostile messages were evaluated as moderately harmful ($M \approx 4.2\text{--}4.5$) and moderately acceptable ($M \approx 3.4\text{--}3.7$). Perceived harmfulness and acceptability were strongly negatively correlated ($r = -.68$), indicating that messages seen as more harmful were generally considered less acceptable. Descriptive statistics for perceived harmfulness and acceptability across message sources are presented in Table 1.

Source	Harmfulness	Acceptability
Politician	4.44 (2.0)	3.55 (2.05)
Journalist	4.49 (2.0)	3.41 (2.05)
Celebrity	4.40 (1.97)	3.56 (2.03)
Unknown	4.22 (1.95)	3.65 (2.01)

Table 1. Means and Standard Deviations of Message Evaluations by Source

Perceived Harmfulness

Perceived harmfulness differed significantly across sources, $F(3, 3054) = 37.25, p < .001$, though effect sizes were modest ($\eta^2 = .04$). Messages attributed to unknown users were perceived as less harmful than those attributed to politicians, journalists, and celebrities. Although statistically significant, differences between sources were small in magnitude (approximately 0.2–0.3 points on a 7-point scale), indicating that source cues exert a limited influence on perceived harmfulness.

Perceived Acceptability

A similar pattern emerged for acceptability, with a significant but small effect of source, $F(3, 3054) = 27.54, p < .001$ ($\eta^2 = .03$). Messages attributed to journalists were perceived as least acceptable, while messages from unknown users were rated as more acceptable than those from institutional sources. As with harmfulness, differences between sources were relatively small in absolute terms (approximately 0.2–0.3 scale points).

Moderation by Threat Perception and Political Orientation

Beyond source effects, individual differences in perceived immigration threat played a substantially larger role. Higher threat perception was strongly associated with lower perceived harmfulness ($\beta = -0.85, p < .001$) and greater acceptability ($\beta = 1.04, p < .001$) of hateful messages. This indicates that individuals who perceive immigration as more threatening are significantly more likely to view hostile rhetoric as acceptable and less harmful.

Political orientation showed a similar, while less strong pattern. More right-leaning individuals perceived hostile messages as less harmful ($\beta = -0.49, p < .001$) and more acceptable ($\beta = 0.54, p < .001$), indicating that ideological predispositions shape responses to immigration-related discourse.

When considered jointly, both threat perception and political orientation remained significant predictors, indicating that ideological predispositions and perceived threat independently shape message evaluations.

Summary of Findings

Overall, while message source has a statistically reliable but modest effect on how hateful immigration messages are evaluated, individual predispositions are far more influential. Perceived immigration threat and political orientation strongly shape whether such messages are seen as harmful or acceptable. These findings suggest that responses to hateful immigration rhetoric depend less on who communicates the message and more on the characteristics of the audience.

It is important to note that the source manipulation relied on generic role labels (e.g., politician, journalist, influencer) without using well-known or highly recognizable figures. As a result, differences in credibility, familiarity, or affect toward specific sources were likely attenuated. In real-world settings, where messages are often associated with recognizable actors, source effects may be stronger than those observed here.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This report examined how socially unacceptable extreme discourses (SUEDs), including hate speech, and populist messaging, shape public perceptions, emotions, and behavioural intentions. By combining cross-national survey data from Belgium and Italy with three experimental studies conducted in Flanders, the findings provide both descriptive and causal evidence on how such content is encountered and processed by the general population.

Key conclusions

First, self-reported exposure to hateful immigration-related content showed no meaningful association with desensitisation, capturing emotional responsiveness to hateful discourse about immigrants, such as finding such content less disturbing. On one hand, it is possible that respondents who are less emotionally affected by hateful content may also be less likely to classify it as hateful when reporting exposure, which could attenuate the observed association. On the other hand, it may point to a more fundamental measurement question: recognised exposure, consciously noticing and labelling content as hateful, may not be the construct most relevant to desensitisation. Emotional numbing may accumulate precisely through repeated contact with content that is not registered as hateful, making it unlikely to be captured by self-report.

Second, desensitisation is strongly linked to behavioural outcomes. Individuals who are more desensitised to hateful content report greater willingness to engage in both activism and more extreme forms of political action. However, given the cross-sectional nature of the data, these relationships should be interpreted as associations rather than causal effects. Alongside these findings, the panel data also revealed consistent differences between Belgium and Italy in exposure levels, activism and radicalism intentions, and contact with immigrants. While the current data do not allow us to explain these differences, they underscore that the impact of SUEDs is not uniform across national contexts.

Third, the experimental findings show that SUEDs likely operate through emotional and perceptual pathways rather than immediate opinion change. Exposure to threat-based framing significantly increased negative emotional responses, particularly anxiety and anger, but did not directly alter attitudes. Instead, emotional reactions were linked to increased perceptions of threat, which in turn predicted more negative attitudes. This indicates that the effects of SUEDs may be also indirect, unfolding through emotional and cognitive processes, though whether these effects accumulate over time remains an open question that longitudinal studies are needed to address.

Fourth, perceived threat plays a central role in structuring political preferences, particularly in differentiating support for political solutions. Higher perceived threat was associated with lower support for humanitarian, left-leaning proposals and higher support for restrictive, right-leaning approaches. One interpretation of this pattern is that restrictive solutions more directly align with threat-based interpretations of immigration by emphasizing control, protection, and risk mitigation, whereas humanitarian approaches may be perceived as less responsive to these concerns.

Finally, while message source has a statistically significant effect, it is comparatively modest, and audience characteristics are far more influential. Messages attributed to unknown sources were perceived as less harmful and more acceptable than those attributed to institutional actors, but these differences were small. In contrast, perceived threat and political orientation strongly shaped responses to hateful messages. This suggests that who receives the message matters more than who delivers it, at least when source cues are generic rather than tied to well-known actors.

Taken together, these findings suggest that the impact of SUEs is shaped less by exposure alone and more by how content is interpreted, particularly through perceptions of threat and underlying predispositions. Rather than producing immediate shifts in opinion, SUEs appear to influence emotional responses, threat perceptions, and evaluative frameworks, which may in turn shape attitudes and behavioural intentions over time.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, several implications can be drawn for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to mitigate the negative effects of socially unacceptable extreme discourses.

1. Address underlying threat perceptions and emotions

The findings indicate that perceived threat and emotional reactions are central to how immigration-related content is interpreted and evaluated. Interventions should therefore go beyond factual correction and engage with how individuals experience and process such content.

Importantly, perceived threat does not need to be based on objectively accurate information to influence attitudes and behaviour. Once an issue is perceived as threatening, corrective information alone may have limited impact.

Potential strategies include:

- Promoting contextualised and credible information about immigration that directly addresses common concerns and perceived threat;
- Developing communication approaches that acknowledge and engage with perceived threat, rather than dismissing it;
- Encouraging meaningful intergroup contact, as direct or indirect contact with immigrants has been linked to more positive perceptions and may reduce perceived threat;
- Supporting local-level initiatives that foster interaction and dialogue between communities, which may help translate abstract threat perceptions into more nuanced understandings.

2. Complement exposure reduction with realistic user strategies

While reducing exposure to harmful content remains important, fully limiting exposure to SUEs is difficult in practice. Harmful content often adapts quickly to platform rules (e.g., through coded language or shifting channels), making complete containment unlikely.

This suggests that content moderation should be complemented by strategies addressing how content is interpreted, rather than relying solely on removal or restriction.

3. Tailor interventions to audience predispositions

The findings show that responses to immigration-related content vary systematically with individual predispositions, particularly perceived threat and political orientation. This implies that interventions should not focus exclusively on message content, but also consider who is receiving it.

It should be noted, however, that threat perceptions and political orientations may in some cases be structurally anchored in identity or ideology, limiting how much they can be shifted through communication alone. With this caveat in mind, potential strategies include:

- Tailoring communication strategies to different audience segments, acknowledging that the same message may be interpreted differently depending on prior dispositions;
- Focusing on groups more responsive to threat-based interpretations, while avoiding stigmatisation;
- Expanding media literacy initiatives to address emotional and cognitive processes, including how prior dispositions and beliefs shape interpretation of content.

4. Recognise the limited but context-dependent role of source cues

While source effects were relatively small in this study, they may be stronger in real-world contexts involving recognizable public figures. Policymakers should:

- Remain attentive to the role of influential actors in amplifying SUEs,
- Consider accountability mechanisms for high-profile communicators,
- Avoid relying on source-based interventions as a primary solution.

5. Monitor desensitisation as a risk factor for radicalisation

Reduced emotional responsiveness to hateful content was consistently associated with more negative stereotypes and greater willingness to support extreme forms of action. While these relationships are correlational, they suggest that desensitisation may serve as a useful indicator of broader attitudinal and behavioural tendencies. Interventions may therefore benefit from:

- Monitoring changes in emotional responsiveness to harmful content over time, for example through repeated surveys;
- Supporting initiatives that maintain sensitivity to harmful discourse without amplifying it.

6. Contextualise interventions within national settings

The findings reveal meaningful differences between countries, cautioning against one-size-fits-all approaches across EU member states. Potential strategies include:

- Treating EU-level recommendations as a framework to be adapted to national contexts rather than applied uniformly;
- Investing in country-specific monitoring of exposure patterns, emotional responses, and behavioral intentions;
- Supporting cross-national research to better understand what contextual factors drive differences across member states, in order to target interventions where they are most needed.

Final takeaway

Overall, mitigating the societal impact of socially unacceptable extreme discourses requires moving beyond a narrow focus on limiting exposure and instead addressing the psychological and social processes through which such content shapes perceptions, emotions and political behaviour within national contexts.

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8. Appendices

Measure Items

A1. Exposure to Hateful Migration-Related Content

Exposure was measured with a single item: “How often do you see hateful or hostile content on social media about immigrants, migrants, or refugees?”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = never, 7 = very often), adapted from Soral et al. (2018).

A2. Desensitisation to Hate

Desensitisation was measured using four items:

- “Seeing hateful comments about immigrants on social media doesn’t really bother me.”
- “When I come across hateful comments about immigrants online, I don’t have much of an emotional reaction.”
- “I feel upset when I see hateful comments about immigrants on social media.” (reverse-coded)
- “Hateful or degrading posts about immigrants don’t seem very serious or harmful to me.”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree).

A3. Stereotypes Toward Immigrants

Stereotypes were measured using a 6-item scale (Asbrock, 2010), capturing two dimensions:

Competence (“Immigrants are competent/competitive/independent.”)

Warmth (“Immigrants are likeable/warm/good-natured.”)

Participants indicated how much each statement reflected their personal perception of immigrants on a 7-point scale (1 = not at all, 7 = completely).

A4. Activism and Radicalism Intentions

Activism and radicalism intentions were measured using an adapted version of the Activism and Radicalism Intention Scale (ARIS; Moskalenko & McCauley, 2009).

Example items include:

- “I would join or belong to an organisation that works to advance my position on the immigration issue.”
- “I would donate money to an organisation working to advance my position on the immigration issue.”
- “I would participate in a protest related to immigration where there is a possibility that violence might occur.”
- “I would support such an organisation even if it sometimes resorts to violence in pursuing its goals.”

All items were measured on a 7-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree).

A5. Contact with Immigrants

Contact with immigrants was measured with two items: “How often do you personally have contact with people with a migration background from other European countries?” and “How often do you personally have contact with people with a migration background from non-European countries?”

Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale: (1 = never, 5 = every day).

A6. Immigration background

Immigration background was measured using two items: “Were you born in [country]?” and “Were your parents born in [country]?”

Response options for the first item were: (1 = yes, 2 = no, born abroad). Response options for the second item were: (1 = both parents born in [country], 2 = one parent born abroad, 3 = both parents born abroad).

A7. Emotional Responses (Experiment 1)

Participants were asked: “Think back to the posts you just viewed. To what extent did you experience the following emotions while viewing the feed?”

Emotions were measured using items from the Discrete Emotion Questionnaire (Harmon-Jones et al., 2016): Anger: anger, mad, pissed off, rage, Anxiety: worry, anxiety, dread, nervous.

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = not at all, 7 = extremely).

A7. Immigration Threat Perception

Threat perception was measured using 12 items adapted from Landmann et al. (2019), capturing six types of threat: symbolic, realistic, safety, cohesion, prejudice, altruistic.

Example items include:

- “Migration is harming Flemish culture.”
- “Migration increases the tax burden on citizens.”
- “Migration leads to an increase in criminal acts.”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree). Items were aggregated into a composite threat perception index.

A8. Immigration Attitudes

Immigration attitudes were measured using four items adapted from Iyengar et al. (2013):

- “Belgium allows too many migrants.”
- “Migration has a positive impact on Belgium.” (reverse-coded)
- “Increased cultural diversity through migration is good for our country.” (reverse-coded)
- “Illegal migration is a major national problem.”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree). Higher scores indicate more negative attitudes toward immigration.

A9. Political Support (Experiment 2)

Political support was measured with a single item: “How likely would you be to support a political party that proposes this solution?”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = very unlikely, 7 = very likely).

A10. Perceived Effectiveness (Experiment 2)

“How effective do you think this solution is in addressing immigration?”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = not at all effective, 7 = very effective).

A11. Perceived Relevance (Experiment 2)

“To what extent does this message address concerns people like you may have about immigration?”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = not at all, 7 = very strongly).

A12. Message Evaluation (Experiment 3)

Perceived harmfulness

“To what extent do you think the above message is harmful?”

Perceived acceptability

“To what extent do you think the above message is acceptable?”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = not at all, 7 = extremely).